

Table 1: Train Set Class Distribution

No	Label	Count	Cumulative %
1	yeroo	168	35.59
2	argachuu	62	48.73
3	seenu	41	57.42
4	hin argatiin	25	62.71
5	qofaa	24	67.80
6	walaalu	21	72.25
7	beeku	19	76.27
8	ummataa	15	79.45
9	tokkummaa	14	82.42
10	biyyaalee	11	84.75
11	qarshii	7	86.23
12	dabarsuu	6	87.50
13	herumaa	5	88.56
14	kanofi gochuu	4	89.41
15	jiraachu	4	90.25
16	guruu	4	91.10
17	mufachuu	4	91.95
18	baachuu	4	92.80
19	biyya lafaa	3	93.43
20	yaadachuu	3	94.07
21	addaan kutu	3	94.70
22	roobaa dhaabu	2	95.13
23	debifachuu	2	95.55
24	hasawuu	2	95.97
25	maqaa	1	96.19
26	simachuu	1	96.40
27	sobu	1	96.61
28	olkaasu	1	96.82
29	fiduu	1	97.03
30	galataa	1	97.25
31	omishaa	1	97.46
32	saamamu	1	97.67
33	xumuraa	1	97.88
34	mudamaa	1	98.09
35	hordofuu	1	98.31
36	ofiraa dabarsuu	1	98.52
37	gaafachuu	1	98.73
38	hojii baddaa	1	98.94
39	hin olu	1	99.15
40	dhufu	1	99.36
41	salphachuu	1	99.58
42	bareessu	1	99.79

43	gurachu	1	100.00
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Table 2: Test Set Class Distribution

No	Label	Count	Cumulative %
1	yeroo	41	29.29
2	argachuu	22	45.00
3	seenu	14	55.00
4	qofaa	9	61.43
5	walaalu	8	67.14
6	tokkummaa	6	71.43
7	beeku	6	75.71
8	hin argatiin	4	78.57
9	biyyaalee	3	80.71
10	biyya lafaa	3	82.86
11	yaadachuu	2	84.29
12	maqaa	2	85.71
13	bareessu	2	87.14
14	ummataa	2	88.57
15	addaan kutu	2	90.00
16	saamamu	2	91.43
17	kanofi gochuu	1	92.14
18	qabu	1	92.86
19	debifachuu	1	93.57
20	boqonnaa	1	94.29
21	gonfachuu	1	95.00
22	baachuu	1	95.71
23	dabarsuu	1	96.43
24	hojii baddaa	1	97.14
25	guruu	1	97.86
26	adda adda	1	98.57
27	ofiraa dabarsuu	1	99.29
28	herumaa	1	100.00

Table 3: Performance comparison of transformer-based and baseline models on the Oromo WSD test set.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
bert-base-cased	0.862470	0.286458	0.331402	0.289660
distilbert-base-multilingual-cased	0.841171	0.250519	0.292299	0.254961
bert-base-uncased	0.849681	0.209132	0.278331	0.230834

SVM	0.780424	0.251656	0.209629	0.218608
Davlan/afro-xlmr-base	0.820935	0.157413	0.209944	0.174136
roberta-base	0.818728	0.151264	0.215174	0.169678
xlm-roberta-base	0.775071	0.100767	0.134616	0.108013
MFS	0.554375	0.023903	0.043116	0.030755

Table 3: Pairwise statistical comparison of model performance based on five-fold cross-validation using Macro-F1 scores. The table reports the mean Macro-F1 score for each model, the difference in performance, Cohen's d effect size, and the p -values obtained from the paired t -test and Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Model A	Model B	Mean Macro F1-A	Mean Macro F1-B	Difference (A-B)	Cohen's d	Effect Size	Paired t-test (p-value)	Wilcoxon (p-value)
bert-base-uncased	bert-base-cased	0.230834	0.289660	-1.612836	-3.606411	0.022629	0.0	0.0625
bert-base-uncased	roberta-base	0.230834	0.169678	0.733356	1.639834	0.176383	3.0	0.3125
bert-base-uncased	xlm-roberta-base	0.230834	0.108013	2.330840	5.211917	0.006463	0.0	0.0625
bert-base-uncased	distilbert-base-multilingual-cased	0.230834	0.254961	-0.368669	-0.824369	0.456049	5.0	0.6250
bert-base-	Davlan/afro-	0.230834	0.174136	0.933220	2.086743	0.105217	1.0	0.1250

Model A	Model B	Mean Macro F1-A	Mean Macro F1-B	Difference (A-B)	Cohen's d	Effect Size	Paired t-test (p-value)	Wilcoxon (p-value)
uncased	xlmr-base							

Table 4: Pairwise statistical comparison of model performance based on five-fold cross-validation using Macro-F1 scores. The table reports the mean Macro-F1 score for each model, the difference in performance, Cohen's d effect size, and the p -values obtained from the paired t -test and Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Model A	Model B	Mean Macro F1-A	Mean Macro F1-B	Difference (A-B)	Cohen's d	Effect Size	Paired t-test (p-value)	Wilcoxon (p-value)
bert-base-cased	RANDOM	0.28966	0.009942	0.279719	7.082079	Large	9.29E-05	0.0625
bert-base-cased	MFS	0.28966	0.030755	0.258905	6.080986	Large	0.000169	0.0625
bert-base-cased	xlm-roberta-base	0.28966	0.108013	0.181647	4.011295	Large	0.000855	0.0625
bert-base-cased	roberta-base	0.28966	0.169678	0.119982	2.008112	Large	0.010904	0.0625
bert-base-cased	Davlan/afro-xlmr-base	0.28966	0.174136	0.115524	1.704872	Large	0.018904	0.0625
bert-base-uncased	bert-base-cased	0.230834	0.28966	-0.05883	-1.61284	Large	0.022629	0.0625
bert-base-cased	SVM	0.28966	0.218608	0.071052	1.03431	Large	0.081781	0.125
bert-base-cased	distilbert-base-multilingual-	0.28966	0.254961	0.0347	0.533287	Medium	0.298982	0.625

	cased							
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Figure 1. Training and validation loss across four fine-tuning epochs for the BERT-base-cased model on the Oromo WSD dataset, illustrating model convergence during training.

Figure 2. Validation Macro-F1 score across four fine-tuning epochs for the BERT-base-cased model, showing progressive improvement in disambiguation performance.

